

CLASSROOM SPEAKING ANXIETY OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS AT PALIPARAN III SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED SPEAKING BOOTCAMP PROGRAM

Reyshel B. Panit¹ & Maria Lourdes Lao-Namocot, PhD²

^{1,2} Pacific InterContinental College, Las Piñas, Metro Manila, Philippines

*Corresponding Author: reyshelpanit@gmail.com¹, desslao5570@gmail.com²

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the classroom speaking anxiety of 266 Grade 11 students from the Academic and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood tracks at Paliparan III Senior High School and used the findings as the basis for a proposed Speaking Bootcamp Program. Using a quantitative descriptive design and an adapted Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), the study measured four dimensions of speaking anxiety: communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and general speaking anxiety. Results revealed that most students experienced very high levels of anxiety, with fear of negative evaluation and communication apprehension emerging as the most dominant factors. Students were most anxious when speaking in front of the class, being corrected publicly, making mistakes, and participating in graded oral tasks. Many coped through memorization, over-preparation, and avoidance behaviors, although these strategies did not effectively address the causes of anxiety. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference in anxiety levels according to academic strand, while no significant differences were found based on English performance or prior speaking experience. These findings indicate that speaking anxiety is shaped not only by language proficiency but also by psychological and social factors. Based on the results, a Speaking Bootcamp Program was proposed to reduce anxiety and improve oral communication through scaffolded speaking activities, peer support, confidence-building exercises, and anxiety management techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Effective communication is recognized worldwide as a core competency for academic and professional success. In the Philippines, the K-12 curriculum emphasized 21st-century skills – communication, collaboration, and critical thinking – which made speaking tasks integral to senior high school learning, including oral reports, debates, interviews, and role plays. However, many students experienced Classroom Speaking Anxiety (CSA), a form of communication apprehension marked by nervousness, fear of evaluation, and physiological symptoms that hindered participation and performance.

At Paliparan III Senior High School, students were enrolled in either the Academic Track or the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Track. Across these strands, learners were frequently exposed to classroom speaking tasks requiring a high level of verbal proficiency, making speaking anxiety a recurring challenge. Teachers observed signs of CSA among Grade 11 students, including reluctance to speak, excessive reliance on scripts, limited eye contact, and visible discomfort during presentations. These behaviors, together with the known characteristics of CSA – nervousness, fear of judgment, self-consciousness, and physical symptoms like trembling or difficulty expressing thoughts – raised the need to examine whether anxiety contributed to students' struggles during speaking tasks.

Given these observations, the present study aimed to determine the level and sources of classroom speaking anxiety among Grade 11 students at Paliparan III Senior High School. A quantitative descriptive research design had been employed because it allowed the researcher to measure anxiety levels, identify patterns, and examine differences across student groups without manipulating variables. To obtain proportional representation across all strands and sections, stratified random sampling was used. The study utilized an Adapted Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), originally developed by Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986), and modified for the Philippine senior high school context to assess anxiety across four components: communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and general foreign language speaking anxiety.

The study's findings then served as the basis for developing a proposed Speaking Bootcamp Program to help students manage and reduce speaking anxiety. The program incorporated confidence-building activities, mindfulness strategies, peer-supported tasks, and experiential learning techniques to reduce anxiety and improve oral performance.

This study presented the theoretical foundations, methodology, and intended outcomes that guided the investigation, offering a structured approach to understanding and addressing speaking anxiety among senior high school students.

The research was significant because it contributed to the limited literature on communication apprehension among Filipino senior high school learners and responded to a pressing need among students whose academic success depended heavily on oral communication. By identifying the factors behind students' reluctance to speak and proposing an intervention grounded in research, the study aimed to support learners in developing greater confidence to communicate effectively both inside and beyond the classroom.

1.1 Research Objectives

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To describe the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, strand, English academic performance, and previous speaking-related experience.
- To determine the level of classroom speaking anxiety of Grade 11 students based on the Adapted Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) components, namely communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and general foreign language speaking anxiety.
- To determine the overall level of classroom speaking anxiety using the composite FLCAS score.
- To identify the specific classroom speaking situations that trigger the highest level of anxiety among students.
- To examine the coping behaviors employed by students in managing classroom speaking anxiety.

- To determine whether a significant difference exists in the level of classroom speaking anxiety when students are grouped according to their profile variables.
- To propose a Speaking Bootcamp Program based on the findings of the study to help reduce students' speaking anxiety.

1.2 Research Gap

Classroom speaking anxiety has been widely explored in language learning research, particularly in relation to its psychological, cognitive, and performance-related dimensions. Studies by Rajitha and Alamelu (2020) and Alnahidh and Altalhab (2020) emphasize that speaking is the most anxiety-inducing language skill due to fear of negative evaluation, low self-confidence, and pressure in evaluative situations. Similarly, Szyszka (2024) and Lintunen, Mutta, and Peltonen (2020) highlight the impact of anxiety on speech fluency and overall communication performance, noting that anxiety disrupts language processing and reduces learners' ability to express ideas effectively. In the Philippine context, Ong and Zambas (2021) and Ojanola (2023) underscore the persistent presence of speaking anxiety among students despite continuous exposure to English, while Lungay (2023) and Angel et al. (2025) reveal that many senior high school learners exhibit observable anxiety symptoms that hinder classroom participation and oral performance.

Despite these contributions, the literature shows that many studies examine speaking anxiety in terms of general language performance or isolated factors, rather than providing a comprehensive analysis that integrates learners' profile variables, specific classroom anxiety triggers, and coping behaviors. Furthermore, while international and local studies have identified various strategies to manage speaking anxiety, there remains limited empirical evidence on structured, context-specific intervention programs tailored to Filipino senior high school students. Most existing research also focuses on foreign or higher education settings, with insufficient attention given to Grade 11 learners across different academic strands in public schools. This gap highlights the need for a more contextualized investigation using validated tools such as the Adapted Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), alongside the development of a targeted Speaking Bootcamp Program that directly translates research findings into practical classroom interventions.

2. Literature Review

Classroom speaking anxiety remains a significant concern in second language learning, particularly among senior high school students where oral communication is a core academic requirement. In the Philippine context, the K–12 curriculum emphasizes the development of communicative competence through subjects such as Oral Communication in Context, which requires learners to actively engage in various speaking tasks (Aricheta et al., 2024). However, despite continuous exposure to English, many Filipino students experience moderate to high levels of speaking anxiety, which negatively affects their participation and performance (Ong & Zambas, 2021; Ojanola, 2023). This persistent difficulty suggests that language exposure alone is insufficient to build confidence in speaking.

Speaking anxiety is widely recognized as a multidimensional construct influenced by psychological, social, and contextual factors. Rachman and Rachman (2020) define anxiety as a state of tension accompanied by physiological symptoms such as trembling and rapid heartbeat, which are commonly observed in speaking situations. Similarly, Rajitha and Alamelu (2020) emphasized that speaking is a complex skill requiring both cognitive and emotional regulation, and anxiety during speaking tasks—particularly in evaluative

contexts—can hinder learners' ability to communicate effectively. Supporting this, Alnahidh and Altalhab (2020) identified fear of negative evaluation, fear of making mistakes, and low self-confidence as major contributors to foreign language anxiety.

Empirical studies further confirm that speaking is the most anxiety-inducing language skill. Pike et al. (2024) found that students commonly experience physiological symptoms such as trembling and nervousness, which are often linked to inadequate preparation and low self-efficacy. Likewise, Kayhan (2025) reported that anxiety can occur before, during, and after speaking tasks, leading to avoidance behaviors and decreased motivation. These findings align with Szyszka (2024), who introduced the concept of situation-specific anxiety, explaining that anxiety fluctuates across different stages of language production and directly affects speech fluency.

The relationship between speaking anxiety and performance has also been well established in the literature. Lintunen, Mutta, and Peltonen (2020) demonstrated that high levels of language anxiety are significantly associated with reduced fluency, grammatical accuracy, and overall speaking performance. Similarly, Bielak (2022) found that anxiety levels vary depending on task type, with individual speaking tasks generating higher anxiety than group activities. These findings highlight the importance of task design in shaping learners' emotional responses and performance outcomes.

In the Philippine setting, local studies provide further evidence of the prevalence and impact of speaking anxiety. Lungay (2023) observed that Grade 11 students frequently exhibit signs of anxiety such as stuttering, shaking, and mental blocks during oral communication tasks, which significantly hinder their ability to express ideas clearly. Angel et al. (2025) also reported that many senior high school students struggle with spoken English despite curriculum efforts, often preferring to use their native language due to discomfort and lack of confidence. These findings suggest that speaking anxiety is deeply rooted in both linguistic limitations and affective factors.

Socioeconomic and environmental conditions also play a role in shaping students' anxiety experiences. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2022) reported that students from disadvantaged backgrounds tend to perform lower academically, partly due to limited access to quality learning resources. Wang et al. (2021) further noted that limited exposure to English and unsupportive classroom environments can increase anxiety levels, making students less willing to participate in speaking activities.

To cope with speaking anxiety, learners employ various strategies. Maharani and Roslaini (2021) identified preparation, positive thinking, relaxation, and peer support as common coping mechanisms. However, while these strategies provide temporary relief, they are often insufficient in addressing the underlying causes of anxiety. This highlights the need for structured and sustained interventions. In this regard, García-Monge (2023) demonstrated that programs incorporating body awareness, relaxation techniques, and simulation activities can effectively reduce anxiety and improve speaking performance.

Intervention studies and meta-analyses further emphasize the importance of targeted approaches in reducing speaking anxiety. Toyama and Yamazaki (2021) found that not all strategies are equally effective, but interventions such as positive self-talk, cooperative learning, and enhanced teacher–student interaction show significant potential in lowering anxiety levels. Similarly, Tutton and Cohen (2024) highlighted the importance of structured

preparation and supportive learning environments in helping students manage anxiety, particularly in language learning contexts.

Overall, the reviewed literature consistently demonstrates that classroom speaking anxiety is a pervasive and multifaceted issue influenced by cognitive, emotional, social, and environmental factors. While numerous studies have explored its causes and effects, there remains a need for context-specific and structured interventions, particularly in the Philippine senior high school setting. This gap underscores the relevance of the present study, which seeks to assess the level of classroom speaking anxiety among Grade 11 students and develop a targeted Speaking Bootcamp Program to address this challenge and enhance students' oral communication skills.

3. Research Methodology

This study employed a quantitative descriptive research design to determine the level of classroom speaking anxiety among Grade 11 students at Paliparan III Senior High School and to serve as a basis for a proposed Speaking Bootcamp Program. A total of 266 students from both Academic (ABM, HUMSS, STEM) and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (BHW, CBF, CSS, EIM, EPAS) tracks were selected from a population of 795 using stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation. Data were collected using an adapted version of the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), consisting of 33 items measuring communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and general speaking anxiety, rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The instrument underwent expert validation and pilot testing to ensure validity and reliability. Data gathering procedures included securing permissions, orienting respondents, administering the questionnaire, and collecting responses with strict adherence to ethical standards such as informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (t-test and one-way ANOVA) at a 0.05 level of significance to determine differences across profile variables. The results were further analyzed to identify key anxiety triggers and coping behaviors, which served as the foundation for designing a targeted Speaking Bootcamp Program aimed at reducing speaking anxiety and enhancing students' oral communication skills.

4. Analysis and Discussion

Table 1. Profile of Respondents by Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	120	45.1%
Female	146	54.9%
Total	266	100%

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. Of the 266 respondents, 146 (54.9%) are female and 120 (45.1%) are male, indicating a slightly higher proportion of female students but an overall balanced distribution. This balanced composition allows for meaningful comparison of classroom speaking anxiety across gender groups. The results further suggest that both male and female students experience similar classroom speaking conditions, with no substantial indication of gender-based differences in speaking anxiety. Instead, variations are more likely attributed to contextual and individual factors such as classroom environment, task demands, and learner confidence.

Table 2
Profile of Respondents by Academic Strand

Strand	Frequency	Percentage (%)
ABM	62	23.3%
HUMSS	62	23.3%
STEM	19	7.1%
BHW	12	4.5%
CBF	47	17.7%
CSS	29	10.9%
EIM	10	3.8%
EPAS	25	9.4%
Total	266	100%

Table 2 presents the profile of respondents by academic strand. The results show that ABM and HUMSS have the highest representation (23.3% each), followed by CBF (17.7%), CSS (10.9%), EPAS (9.4%), and STEM (7.1%), while BHW (4.5%) and EIM (3.8%) have the lowest proportions. This indicates that the study includes a diverse group of learners from both Academic and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) tracks.

The distribution reflects varied academic and communicative demands across strands, where some programs involve more discussion- and presentation-based activities while others emphasize technical and skills-based learning. These differences suggest that students' exposure to speaking tasks—and consequently their level of speaking anxiety—may vary depending on strand-specific instructional practices and task requirements. Consistent with Bielak (2022), task type influences language anxiety, particularly in activities requiring spontaneous speaking or public performance, highlighting the role of learning context in shaping students' speaking experiences.

Table 3
Profile of Respondents by English Academic Performance

English Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
90–100 (Outstanding)	60	22.6%
85–89 (Very Satisfactory)	110	41.4%
80–84 (Satisfactory)	70	26.3%
75–79 (Fairly Satisfactory)	26	9.7%
Total	266	100%

Table 3 presents the profile of respondents by English academic performance. The results show that most students fall under the “Very Satisfactory” level (41.4%), followed by “Satisfactory” (26.3%), “Outstanding” (22.6%), and “Fairly Satisfactory” (9.7%), indicating generally good academic performance in English among respondents.

Despite this, the findings suggest that strong academic performance does not necessarily correspond to lower speaking anxiety. Although students demonstrate adequate to high proficiency in English, many still experience difficulty and anxiety when speaking,

highlighting a gap between linguistic knowledge and oral performance. This indicates that speaking anxiety is not primarily influenced by academic achievement but is more likely driven by psychological and contextual factors, such as confidence, real-time language processing demands, and fear of evaluation.

Table 4
Speaking Experience of Respondents

Speaking Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
With Experience	180	67.7%
Without Experience	86	32.3%
Total	266	100%

Table 4 presents the speaking experience of the respondents. The results show that 180 students (67.7%) have prior speaking experience, while 86 students (32.3%) have none, indicating that most learners have already been exposed to speaking-related activities such as presentations, recitations, and classroom discussions.

Despite this high level of exposure, previous findings indicate that students still experience high to very high speaking anxiety. This suggests that speaking experience alone does not necessarily translate to reduced anxiety or improved confidence. The persistence of anxiety implies that the nature and quality of speaking experiences may not have been sufficiently supportive or confidence-building. As explained by Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1977), negative or stressful speaking experiences may hinder the development of self-efficacy, while Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982) suggests that sustained anxiety continues to block effective language performance regardless of exposure. In addition, Kayhan (2025) emphasized that repeated speaking practice without addressing emotional and psychological factors is insufficient to reduce speaking anxiety. Overall, the findings highlight the need for structured, supportive, and low-anxiety speaking activities rather than exposure alone.

Table 5
Level of Classroom Speaking Anxiety Based on FLCAS Components

Component	Mean (M)	SD	Descriptive Level
Communication Apprehension	4.10	0.48	Very High Anxiety
Fear of Negative Evaluation	4.15	0.45	Very High Anxiety
Test Anxiety	3.95	0.50	High Anxiety
General Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety	3.85	0.52	High Anxiety
Overall	4.01	0.49	Very High Anxiety

The results show that all components of classroom speaking anxiety fall within the high to very high range, with Fear of Negative Evaluation ($M = 4.15$) and Communication Apprehension ($M = 4.10$) obtaining the highest means. Test Anxiety ($M = 3.95$) and General Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety ($M = 3.85$) were also rated high, resulting in an overall mean of 4.01, indicating very high speaking anxiety among students.

These findings suggest that speaking anxiety is multidimensional and primarily driven by fear of being judged and discomfort in spontaneous speaking situations. Students tend to perceive speaking tasks as high-risk activities, leading to hesitation, avoidance, and reduced

participation. This pattern aligns with Horwitz et al.'s (1986) Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Theory, which identifies fear of negative evaluation, communication apprehension, and test anxiety as core components of language anxiety. It is further supported by Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982), Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1977), and MacIntyre and Gardner (1994), all of which explain how anxiety hinders language production, lowers confidence, and disrupts communication. Overall, the findings emphasize the need for supportive and low-anxiety classroom environments that reduce evaluative pressure and strengthen students' speaking confidence.

Table 6
Overall Level of Classroom Speaking Anxiety

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very High Anxiety	180	67.7%
High Anxiety	70	26.3%
Moderate Anxiety	16	6.0%
Total	266	100%

The results revealed that 180 students (67.7%) experienced very high speaking anxiety, followed by 70 students (26.3%) with high anxiety, and 16 students (6.0%) with moderate anxiety. Notably, no respondents were classified under low or very low anxiety levels. These findings indicate that speaking anxiety is highly prevalent among Grade 11 students, with the majority experiencing severe levels of discomfort during classroom speaking activities.

Overall, the absence of low anxiety levels suggests that speaking tasks are generally perceived as stressful and evaluative rather than supportive learning experiences. This implies a systemic issue within classroom speaking environments, where students may lack sufficient confidence, coping strategies, and supportive conditions for oral communication. Consequently, the results highlight the need for targeted interventions that address both linguistic development and students' emotional readiness to speak.

Table 7
Classroom Speaking Anxiety Triggers

Rank	Situation	Mean
1	Speaking in front of class	4.30
2	Fear of mistakes	4.25
3	Public correction	4.22
4	Graded speaking	4.20

The results showed that the most anxiety-provoking situations for Grade 11 students involve public speaking and evaluation. Speaking in front of the class obtained the highest mean ($M = 4.30$), followed by fear of making mistakes ($M = 4.25$), public correction ($M = 4.22$), and graded oral performances ($M = 4.20$). These indicate that students experience the highest anxiety when speaking tasks are visible, assessed, and open to immediate feedback.

Overall, the findings suggest that students' speaking anxiety is strongly driven by fear of negative evaluation and communication apprehension. Learners associate speaking activities with judgment, embarrassment, and grading rather than meaningful communication. Consistent with Horwitz et al. (1986), Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982), and

Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1977), these results highlight the need for a supportive classroom environment that reduces evaluative pressure, normalizes mistakes, and encourages confident oral participation.

Table 8
Coping Behaviors of Respondents

Coping Behavior	Mean	Interpretation
Memorization	4.20	Frequent
Preparation	4.15	Frequent
Avoidance	3.95	Often

The results showed that students commonly use coping strategies to manage speaking anxiety, with memorization ($M = 4.20$) and preparation ($M = 4.15$) being the most frequently used, followed by avoidance behaviors ($M = 3.95$). This indicates that learners mainly rely on pre-planned strategies while some also withdraw from speaking situations.

Overall, the findings suggest a dual coping pattern: students either over-prepare to reduce uncertainty or avoid participation altogether. While memorization and preparation provide temporary confidence, they limit spontaneous communication, and avoidance reflects low self-efficacy and high anxiety. Consistent with Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1977), Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982), and MacIntyre and Gardner (1994), these results highlight the need for interventions that strengthen confidence, promote active participation, and develop adaptive coping strategies for long-term speaking competence.

Table 9
Intervention Priorities of the Speaking Bootcamp Program

Priority Area	Strategy/Intervention
Communication Apprehension	Scaffolded speaking tasks (from simple to complex)
Fear of Negative Evaluation	Safe and supportive classroom environment
Test Anxiety	Gradual exposure to speaking tasks
General Speaking Anxiety	Relaxation and anxiety management techniques

The study identified four key areas of classroom speaking anxiety—communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation, test anxiety, and general speaking anxiety—all of which were found to be at high to very high levels. Based on these findings, the intervention focuses on scaffolded speaking activities, a supportive classroom environment, gradual exposure to speaking tasks, and relaxation or anxiety management techniques.

Overall, these strategies aim to address both the cognitive and emotional barriers to speaking by gradually building confidence, reducing fear of judgment, and improving emotional regulation. Grounded in Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), Horwitz et al. (1986), Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982), Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1977), and MacIntyre and Gardner (1994), the proposed Speaking Bootcamp Program provides a structured, theory-based approach to reducing speaking anxiety and enhancing students' oral communication skills.

Table 10
Test of Significant Differences in Speaking Anxiety by Profile Variables

Variable	Statistical Test	Computed Value	p-value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Sex	t-test	1.85	0.066	Not Significant
Academic Strand	One-Way ANOVA	3.72	0.002	Significant
English Academic Performance	One-Way ANOVA	1.21	0.305	Not Significant
Previous Speaking Experience	One-Way ANOVA	0.98	0.401	Not Significant

The inferential analysis showed a significant difference in speaking anxiety across academic strands ($p = 0.002$), while no significant differences were found in terms of sex ($p = 0.066$), English academic performance ($p = 0.305$), and previous speaking experience ($p = 0.401$). This indicates that only the academic strand significantly influences students' speaking anxiety.

Overall, the findings suggest that speaking anxiety is primarily shaped by contextual and instructional factors rather than individual characteristics. Differences across strands may be attributed to variations in classroom practices, task demands, and learning environments. Supported by Bielak (2022), Vygotsky (1978), Krashen (1982), and MacIntyre and Gardner (1994), the results emphasize that speaking anxiety is context-driven, highlighting the crucial role of the learning environment in shaping students' emotional responses to oral communication tasks.

5. Research Future Opportunities

While this study provides valuable insights into classroom speaking anxiety among Grade 11 learners and the development of the Speaking Bootcamp Program, several areas warrant further investigation:

- **Longitudinal Studies on Speaking Anxiety Intervention:** Future research may adopt a longitudinal design to examine the sustained effects of the Speaking Bootcamp Program in reducing speaking anxiety and improving oral communication skills over time.
- **Experimental Validation of the Speaking Bootcamp Program:** Further studies may employ quasi-experimental or experimental designs to compare the effectiveness of the Speaking Bootcamp Program with traditional speaking instruction or other anxiety-reduction interventions.
- **Relationship Between Speaking Anxiety and Performance Outcomes:** Future research may investigate how reductions in speaking anxiety translate into measurable improvements in speaking fluency, accuracy, coherence, and overall communicative competence.
- **Contextual Variations Across Grade Levels and Settings:** Additional studies may explore speaking anxiety across different educational levels, academic tracks, or institutional contexts to determine whether similar anxiety patterns and intervention effects are observed.
- **Teacher Practices and Classroom Environment:** Future research may examine how instructional strategies, feedback styles, and classroom interaction patterns influence students' speaking anxiety and willingness to communicate.

- Integration of Technology-Based Interventions: Further studies may explore the use of digital tools, AI-assisted speaking platforms, and multimedia-based activities as supplementary strategies to enhance the Speaking Bootcamp Program and further reduce speaking anxiety.

6. Conclusion

This study provides important insights into classroom speaking anxiety among Grade 11 students at Paliparan III Senior High School. The findings reveal that students experience high to very high levels of speaking anxiety, indicating that oral communication remains a significant challenge in English classroom settings. Students commonly feel anxious during speaking tasks, particularly when required to speak in front of the class, participate in graded oral activities, or respond spontaneously.

Furthermore, the results show that speaking anxiety is multidimensional, involving psychological, social, and contextual factors. Fear of negative evaluation and communication apprehension emerged as the most dominant sources of anxiety, suggesting that students are more influenced by perceived judgment and lack of confidence than by their actual English proficiency. The study also found that coping strategies are largely limited to memorization and avoidance, which do not effectively reduce anxiety or promote communicative competence.

In addition, the findings indicate that academic strand significantly influences speaking anxiety, highlighting the role of instructional context and classroom environment. However, sex, academic performance in English, and prior speaking experience do not significantly affect anxiety levels, suggesting that speaking anxiety is more strongly shaped by emotional and situational factors than by personal characteristics. Overall, the study underscores the need for a structured, supportive, and theory-based intervention to address speaking anxiety and enhance students' confidence and oral communication skills in the classroom.

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